

INVENTORY OF NANTUCKET MACROFUNGI

Dr. Lawrence Millman

Nantucket's plant diversity might suggest an equivalent diversity of fungal species, since diversity in fungi is often predicated on diversity either in host plants, if the fungus is parasitic, or in symbiotic partners, if the fungus has an ectomycorrhizal relationship with a tree or plant. Yet despite the @200 species listed in the following inventory, the island doesn't have the fungal diversity of less botanically rich areas on the mainland. There are several possible reasons for this:

- (1) Nantucket's winds dry out potential fungal substrates, thus inhibiting fungal growth. If a species does succeed in fruiting/sporulating, its spores will probably end up quite a distance from their fruiting body, and thus at a remove from the appropriate ectomycorrhizal partner and/or substrate.
- (2) Being a terminal moraine, Nantucket's soil tends to be sandy and porous. Such soils are usually devoid of most of the nutrients necessary for fungal growth.
- (3) Dead trees on the island are seldom left to decay in situ, so the variety of sapro-trophic wood rotters that exist in many other parts of the Northeast are absent on Nantucket.
- (4) The sea is a dispersal barrier for the spores of mainland species.

But four hundred years of human habitation, not to mention human visitation, have created a different type of fungal diversity on the island. My inventory includes a disproportionately large percentage of (among others) puffball species and *Amanita* species, both of which have evolved to distill nutrients from poor, disturbed, or artificial substrates, such as, respectively, trails, pastures, and gardens. That most of the species in this inventory were found in Squam Swamp, Lost Farm, and Hidden Forest does not deny the significance of disturbed areas as fungal habitats on Nantucket.

Many ectomycorrhizal species commonly found in northeastern forests -- like, for example, boletes -- aren't particularly common on Nantucket. Not surprisingly, the island's most common bolete, *Boletus parasiticus*, is not typically a forest species. Rather, it parasitizes a *Scleroderma* puffball which itself inhabits poor soils or disturbed areas. *B. parasiticus* would seem to occur much less frequently on the mainland than it does on Nantucket.

Likewise, some of the island's fungal diversity would seem to be random, at the mercy of storms, the winds, and the spore-vectoring talents of tourists' footwear. This would help explain why certain species fruit on Nantucket in very small quantities or in isolation from each other. It would also help explain why there's not a larger overlap between my inventory and the only previous inventory, Dr. Emil Guba's, done between 1937-1942 and published in *Rhodora*. (Note: Dr. Guba's inventory included mold and rust species, but I haven't.)

An inventory of this type is necessarily limited: I visited Nantucket at least once a year for six years, between June 2004 and October 2009, frequently during very dry periods, while an ideal survey would encompass a period of at least ten years, with weekly visits to the study site. Thus the aforementioned

generalizations must remain just that -- generalizations, not absolute facts. Still, I would like to think that this study will provide a useful foundation for future studies of fungi on Nantucket.

INVENTORY OF NANTUCKET FUNGI; 6/04 to 9/08

Compiled by Dr. Lawrence Millman

- Agaricus arvensis* (Horse Mushroom). Meadow and grassy areas. Squam Farm
Agaricus campestris (Meadow Mushroom). Grass in Quaker Cemetery.
Agaricus placomyces. On ground. Lost Farm.
Agaricus porphyrocephala. Grass and sandy soil. Quaise and Squam Farm
Agaricus silvaticus (Red-Staining Agaricus). Squam Swamp.
Agrocybe dura. On wood chips. Tuppenny Links. Spring.
Agrocybe praecox (Spring Agrocybe). On woody debris. Squam Swamp. Spring.
Amanita bisporigera (=virosa) Under pine. Coskata Woods. Infrequent. (9/05)
Amanita brunnescens (Cleft Foot). In wooded areas around Nantucket.
Amanita citrina (Citron Amanita). Oak and pine woods. Common around Nantucket.
Amanita cokeri (Coker's Amanita). In woods. Lost Farm.
Amanita crenulata. Under white pine. State Forest. Infrequent. (9/05)
Amanita fulva (Tawny Grisette). Near tupelo. Squam Swamp.
Amanita gemmata (Gemmed Amanita). In grass near Tom Nevers Road. Also Tuckernuck.
Amanita inaurata (Strangulated Amanita). Under white pine. State Forest.
Amanita muscaria var. formosa (Fly Agaric). With pine, esp. pitch pine. Lost Farm and Coskata Woods.
Amanita rubescens (The Blusher). In mixed woods. Frequent.
Amanita rubescens var. alba. In wooded area. Squam Farm. Infrequent. (10/07)
Amanita vaginata (Grisette). State Forest. Frequent.
Antrodia albida. On white pine logs. State Forest and Hidden Forest.
Arcyria denudata (Purple Slime). Well-rotted log. Hidden Forest.
Armillaria ostoyae. On stump. Squam Farm. Infrequent (10/09)
Armillariella mellea (Honey Mushroom). On wood and woody debris. Frequent.
Ascocoryne cylichnum. On rotten hardwood log. Squam Swamp.
Asterophora lycoperdoides (Powder Cap). On rotting *Russula* species. State Forest.
Astraeus hygrometricus (Barometer Earthstar). On trail. State Forest.
Auricularia auricula (Wood Ear). On pine log. Squam Swamp.
Bisporella citrina (Lemon Drops). On decorticated wood. Frequent.
Bjerkandera adusta (Smoky Polypore). Oak logs. Squam Swamp.
Boletinellus (=Gyrodon) *merulioides* (Ash Tree Bolete). Near ash. Squam Swamp.
Boletellus chrysenteroides (Cracked Cap Bolete). Near tupelo. Squam Swamp.
Boletus (=Xanthoconium) *affinis var. maculosus* (Spotted Bolete). Under beech. State Forest.
Boletus bicolor (Two Colored Bolete). Under oak. State Forest.
Boletus parasiticus. Parasitic on *Scleroderma* species. Lost Farm and Squam Farm.
Bovista pila (Tumbling Puffball). Sandy soil. Lost Farm.
Bulgaria inquinans (Black Jelly Drops). On beech(?) branch. Near Oldest House. Infrequent (10/09)
Calocera cornea (Tuning Fork). Decorticated logs. Squam Swamp.
Calvatia cyathiformis (Purple Spored Puffball). In grass near Oldest House. Infrequent. (10/07)
Cantharellus cibarius (Chanterelle). Tuckernuck.
Cantharellus minor (Small Chantarelle). In moss. Squam Swamp.

Ceratiomyxa fruticulosa (Coral Slime). On rotten wood. Frequent.
Cerrena unicolor (Mossy Maze Polypore). On deciduous wood. Frequent.
Cheimonophyllum candidissimus (White Oysterette). On tupelo log. Squam Swamp.
Chlorociboria chlora. On decorticated wood. In swamp. Tuckernuck.
Clavicornia pyxidata (Crown Tipped Coral). On poplar logs. Hidden Forest.
Clavulina cinerea (Grey Coral). In swamp. Tuckernuck.
Clavulinopsis fusiformis (Golden Spindles). In moss. Squam Swamp.
Clavulinopsis aurantiocinnabarina. In moss. Squam Swamp. Infrequent. (9/04)
Clitocybe clavipes (Club Foot). Under white pine. State Forest.
Clitocybe nuda (Blewit). Woody debris. Hidden Forest and Squam Swamp.
Collybia acervata (Clustered Collybia). Wood mulch. Nantucket town.
Collybia dryophila (Oak Loving Collybia). With oak. Frequent.
Collybia maculata (Spotted Collybia). On humus. Lost Farm.
Collybia maculata var. scorzonerea. On humus/grass. Lost Farm. Infrequent. (9/05)
Collybia tuberosa. On decayed mushrooms. Quaise.
Collyia (=butyracea) (Buttery Collybia). With pitch pine. Lost Farm.
Coltricia perennis. On ground. Lost Farm.
Coprinus atramentarius (Tippler's Bane). On woody debris. Common around Nantucket.
Coprinus plicatilis (Japanese Umbrella Inky). On mulch in front of Drake House. Infrequent. (5/04)
Coprinus quadrifidus (Scaly Inky Cap). On mulch pile. Tuppenny Links. Infrequent. (5/04)
Cortinarius alboviolaceus (Silvery Violet Cort). Under beech. Squam Swamp.
Cortinarius caninus (Dog Cort). Squam Swamp.
Cortinarius iodes (Viscid Violet Cort). In forested areas. Frequent.
Cortinarius pseudosalor. Near hemlock. Quaise.
Cortinarius semisanguineus (Red-Gilled Cort). On ground. Lost Farm.
Craterellus fallax (Black Trumpet). Near oak and beech. Squam Swamp.
Crepidotus applanatus (Flat Crep). Red maple log. Hidden Forest.
Crepidotus mollis (Jelly Crep). Maple and oak logs. Squam Swamp.
Cribraria argillacea (slime mold). Well-rotted pine log. Squam Swamp.
Crucibulum laeve (White Bird's Nest). On woody debris, esp. in Nantucket town.
Cryptoporus volvatus (Veiled Polypore). On Japanese black pine at Tuppenny Links. Infrequent. (5/04)
Cystoderma amianthinum var. amianthinum. On woody debris. State Forest.
Daedalea quercina (Thick Maze Polypore). On oak logs. Tuppenny Links.
Daedaleopsis confragosa (Thin Maze Polypore). On deciduous wood. Frequent.
Daldinia concentrica (Carbon Balls). On dead scrub oak branches. Middle Moors.
Entoloma arbortivum (Aborted Entoloma). On woody debris. Squam Swamp.
Entoloma sinuatum (=lividum). (Lead Poisoner) Squam Swamp.
Entoloma strictius (Straight Stalked Entoloma). On rotting wood. Squam Swamp.
Exidia glandulosa (Black Witch's Butter). On oak logs. Squam Swamp.
Exobasidium rhododendrii (Azalea Gall). On wild azalea. Squam Swamp. Infrequent. (5/04)
Favolus alveolaris (Hexagonal Pored Polypore). On deciduous wood branches. Coskata Woods.
Fuligo septica (Scrambled Egg Slime). On logs and leaf litter. Squam Swamp.
Galerina autumnalis (Deadly Galerina). On rotting log. Squam Swamp.
Galerina paludosa. On moss. Squam Swamp.
Ganoderma lucidum (Ling Chih). On scrub oak logs. Middle Moors.
Ganoderma tsugae (Hemlock Varnish Shelf). On Japanese black pine. Tuppenny Links.

Geastrum saccatum (Rounded Earthstar). In dunes. Surfside Beach.
Gelatinosus geoglossi. Parasitic on *Trichoglossum* sp. Squam Swamp.
Gloeophyllum sepiarium (Yellow-Red Gill Polypore). On white pine log. Lost Farm.
Grifola frondosa (Hen of the Woods). On dead oak stump. Hidden Forest.
Gymnopilus penetrans (Little Gym). On dead coniferous wood. State Forest. Frequent.
Gymnosporangium juniperus-virginiae. On juniper needles. Dead Horse Valley.
Haemostereum sanguinolentum (Bleeding Stereum). On beech log near State Forest.
Hebeloma crustuliniforme (Poison Pie). Under pitch pine in front of Nantucket airport.
Hemitrichia serpula (Pretzel Slime). On rotten wood. Hidden Forest.
Hydnellum scrobiculatum var. *zonatum*. On ground. Squam Swamp. Infrequent (10/09)
Hydnochaete olivaceum (Brown Toothed Crust). On dead deciduous branches. Frequent.
Hydnochaete tabacina (Reddish Brown Crust). Beech branches. Squam Swamp.
Hydnum (=Dentinum) repandum (Sweet Tooth). Near hemlock. Squam Swamp.
Hydnum (=Dentinum) repandum var. *album*. Near hemlock. Squam Swamp. Infrequent. (9/05)
Hygrocybe borealis (=niveus) (White Waxy Cap). In moss. Frequent.
Hygrocybe canescens. Near hemlock. Squam Swamp. Infrequent. (9/05)
Hygrocybe coccinea (Scarlet Waxy Cap). In swamp areas of Squam Swamp.
Hygrocybe flavescens (Golden Waxy Cap). In moss. Squam Swamp and Tuckernuck Island.
Hygrocybe marginata (Orange Gilled Waxy Cap). In wooden areas. Frequent.
Hygrocybe nitidus. On leaf litter. Squam Swamp.
Hygrocybe psitticinus (Parrot Mushroom). In moss and leaf litter. Squam Swamp.
Hygrocybe unguinosus. In swamp. Tuckernuck.
Hygrophoropsis aurantiaca (False Chanterelle). Around white pine. State Forest. Frequent.
Hygrophorus eburneus (White Waxy Cap). Coskata Woods.
Hypholoma fasciculare (Sulphur Tuft). Woody debris. Squam Swamp.
Hypholoma sublateritium (Brick Tops). On rotting wood. Frequent.
Hypholoma udum. In wet moss. Squam Swamp.
Hypocrea gelatinosa (Yellow Cushion). On rotting wood. Squam Swamp.
Hypomyces chrysospermus (Golden Hypomyces). On Bolete species. Quaise. Infrequent. (10/07)
Hypoxyton annulatum. On black oak stumps. Tuckernuck Island.
Hypoxyton fragiforme. On dead beech logs. Frequent.
Inonotus (=Onnia) tomentosus (Woolly Velvet Polypore). Under pitch pine. Lost Farm.
Irpex lacteus (Milk White Toothed Polypore). On dead deciduous wood. Frequent.
Laccaria laccata (Common Laccaria). In poor or sandy soil. Frequent.
Laccaria longipes. With sphagnum moss. Tuckernuck. Infrequent (8/08)
Laccaria trullisata (Sand Loving Laccaria). Sandy soil. Coskata.
Lactarius deceptivus (Deceptive Milky). With oak. Squam Swamp.
Lactarius deliciosus (=deterimus) (Orange Latex Milky). With white pine. Tuckernuck.
Lactarius lignyotus (Chocolate Milky). Under white pine. State Forest.
Lactarius luteolus (Buff Fishy Milky). With scrub oak. Tuckernuck.
Lactarius vinaceorufescens (Yellow Latex Milky). Under pine. Frequent.
Laetiporus sulphureus (Chicken of the Woods). Oak log. Squam Swamp.
Laxitextum roseo-carneum. On decaying hardwood branches. Quaise.
Leccinum aurantiacum (Red-Capped Scaber Stalk). With pitch pine. Sand plain in Madasket.
Leccinum insigne (Aspen Scaber Stalk). Under poplar. Lost Farm.
Leocarpis fragilis (Insect Egg Slime). On rotten wood. Squam Swamp.

Lepiota cristata (Malodorous Lepiota). Mulch pile. Lost Farm. Infrequent. (9/05)
Lepiota naucinoides (Smooth Lepiota). On disturbed ground. Squam Farm.
Lycogala epidendrum (Wolf's Milk Slime). On dead wood. Common around Nantucket.
Lycoperdon gemmatum (Gemmed Puffball). On trail. Squam Farm.
Lycoperdon marginatum (local name: Sheep's Knuckles). Sand or sandy soil. Frequent.
Lycoperdon pyriforme (Pear Shaped Puffball). On stumps and debris in forested areas.
Marasmius oreades (Fairy Ring Mushroom). In grass. Mormon Cemetery.
Maramius scorodiscus (Garlic Marasmius). In grass. Old Quaker Cemetery.
Mollisia cinerea (Grey Cup). Under dead logs in wet areas.
Mutinus caninus (Dog Stinkhorn). Dunes. Infrequent. (9/07)
Mutinus elegans (Devil's Dipstick). Sand plain in Madasket.
Mycena galericulata (Common Mycena). On deciduous and coniferous wood. Squam Swamp.
Mycena haematopus (Bleeding Mycena). On maple logs. Squam Swamp and Hidden Forest.
Nolanea quadrata (Salmon Unicorn Entoloma). In moss. Squam Swamp.
Nolanea lutea. On ground. Squam Swamp. Infrequent. (9/06)
Nolanea murraini (Yellow Unicorn Entoloma). On ground. Squam Swamp.
Oligoporus fragilis (Brown Staining Polypore). On white pine logs. State Forest.
Oxyporus populinus (Mossy Maple Polypore). On maple. State Forest and Coskata Woods.
Panaeolus campanulatus (Bell-Cap Panaeolus). On horse dung. State Forest. Infrequent. (10/07)
Panellus stipticus (Luminescent Panellus). On dead wood. Frequent.
Peziza varia. On mulch pile. Tuppenny Links. Infrequent. (5/06)
Phaeolus schweinitzii (Dyer's Polypore). At base of pine trees. Squam Swamp.
Phaeocalicium polyporaenum. On caps of *Trichaptum bififormis*. Frequent.
Phanerochaete chrysorhiza (Spreading Yellow Tooth). Underside of deciduous logs. Squam Swamp.
Phellinus ferruginosus. On oak(?) branch. Near State Forest.
Pholiota aurivella (Golden Pholiota). On dead maple. Squam Swamp.
Phyllotopsis nidulans (Orange Mock Oyster). On scrub oak branch. Quaise.
Pluteus cervinus (Fawn Mushroom). On maple logs. Squam Swamp.
Polyporus brumalis (Winter Polypore). On birch log. Hidden Forest.
Polyporus squamosus (Dryad's Saddle). On buried wood near Jared Coffin House and in Coskata.
Psathyrella delineata. On tupelo stump. Squam Swamp.
Psathyrella foenicisecii (Lawn Mower's Mushroom). In grassy areas around Nantucket. Spring.
Psathyrella hydrophila (Clustered Psathyrella). On maple logs and stumps. Hidden Forest.
Psilocybe atrobrunnea. In sphagnum. Squam Swamp. Infrequent. (9/05)
Ramaria stricta (Straight Branches Coral). Under pine. Squam Swamp.
Ramariopsis kunzei (White Coral). On ground. Squam Swamp. Infrequent. (9/06)
Resupinatus applicatus (Black Jelly Oyster). On beech branch near Oldest House. Infrequent (10/09)
Rhytisma acerinum (Tar Spot of Maple). On maple leaves. Frequent.
Russula crustosa (Green Quilt Russula). Under oak. Squam Swamp.
Russula dissimulans (Blackening Russula). Near white pine. State Forest.
Russula emetica (Emetic Russula). In forested areas around Nantucket.
Russula laurocerasi (Almond Scented Russula). Under or near maple. Lost Farm.
Russula violacea (= *krombholzii*). (Blackish Red Russula). In woods. Quaise.
Sarcodon (= *Hydnellum*) *scabrosus*. Under scrub oak. Tuckernuck. Uncommon (8/08)
Schizophyllum commune (Split Gill). On branches and dead logs. Hidden Forest and Tuppenny Links.
Scleroderma areolatum. In parking area. Squam Swamp.

Scleroderma bovista. Sandy soil. Tuckernuck Island.
Scleroderma cepa (Hardball). Woodchips in front of Hyline office, Nantucket town.
Scleroderma citrinum (Pigskin Poison Puffball). In sandy soil around Nantucket. Frequent.
Scleroderma meridionale. On disturbed ground. Lost Farm.
Scleroderma polyrhizon (=geaster). Sand and gravel. Tuckernuck Island.
Scutellinia scutellata (Eyelash Cup). On rotting logs. Hidden Forest and Squam Swamp.
Stemonitis splendens (Chocolate Tube Slime). Red maple log. Hidden Forest.
Stereum complicatum (Crowded Parchment). On dead wood. Frequent.
Stereum ostrea (False Turkey Tail). On dead wood. Frequent.
Stereum rugosum. On dead swamp maple tree. Hidden Forest. Infrequent. (9/06)
Strobilomyces floccopus (Old Man of the Woods). With white pine(?). Lost Farm.
Stropharia rugosoannulata (Wine Cap). In wood chips and gardens around Nantucket town.
Suillus granulatus (Granulated Suillus). Under white pine. Common in forested areas.
Suillus luteus (Slippery Jack). Under white pine and pitch pine in State Forest.
Suillus neoalbidipes. Under white pine. State Forest. Infrequent (10/09)
Thelephora terrestris (Earth Vase). In sandy soil. Tuckernuck Island and Lost Farm
Trametes conchifer (Little Nest Polypore). On beech branch. Main Street.
Trametes hirsuta (Hairy Turkey Tail). On dead deciduous wood or in wounds. State Forest.
Trametes ochracea (Yellow Turkey Tail). On maple log. Squam Swamp. Infrequent. (10/07)
Trametes pubescens. On tupelo logs. Squam Swamp.
Trametes versicolor (Turkey Tail). On dead deciduous wood. Frequent.
Tremella mesenterica (Witch's Butter). On dead wood. Hidden Forest.
Tremella reticulata. On wood. Squam Swamp. Infrequent. (9/06)
Tremellodendron pallidum (=schweinitzii). Near tupelo. Squam Swamp.
Trichaptum abietinum. On coniferous logs. Hidden Forest and Squam Swamp.
Trichaptum bififormis (Purple Toothed Polypore). On dead deciduous stumps and logs. Frequent.
Trichoglossum farlowii. In wet moss. Squam Swamp.
Trichoglossum hirsutum (Hairy Earth Tongue). In wet moss. Squam Swamp.
Trichoglossum walteri. In moss. Squam Swamp.
Tricholoma resplendens (=columbetta). (White Trich) Under pine. Hidden Forest.
Tricholoma sejunctum. Under pine. Hidden Forest.
Tricholoma vaccinum (Russet-Scaly Trich). In sheep pen. On woody debris. Lost Farm.
Tylopilus alboater. Under oak. Coskata Woods. Infrequent. (9/05)
Tylopilus badiceps. Probably with oak. Lost Farm. Infrequent (8/08)
Tylopilus felleus (Bitter Bolete). In wooded areas around Nantucket.
Tyromyces chioneus (White Cheese Polypore). Dead deciduous wood. Hidden Forest and Squam Swamp.
Ustulina deusta (Carbon Cushion). On living maple. Squam Swamp.
Ustulina deusta (asexual stage). On dead tupelo log. Squam Swamp. Infrequent. (10/07)

Additions, early Nov. 2008

Apiosporina morbosa (Black Knot of Cherry). Dead cherry. Lost Farm.
Chlorenchocelia (=Chlorosplenium) versiforme. Decorticated wood. Squam Swamp.
Hypholoma capnoides. On white pine. Squam Swamp.
Lactarius peckii (Peck's Lactarius). Under oak. State Forest.
Multiclavula mucida (White-Green Algae Coral). On algae-covered wood. Hidden Forest.
Mycena griseoviridis. On oak. Squam Swamp.

Oligoporus tephroleucus. On downed swamp maple. Hidden Forest. Infrequent (10/08)
Panellus serotinus (Late Fall Oyster). On rotting log. Hidden Forest.
Polyporus brumalis (Winter Polypore). On birch log. Squam Swamp.
Serpula lacrymans (Dry Rot). Under board. Quaise.
Skeletocutis nivea. Under oak log. State Forest.
Stereum hirsutum (Hairy False Turkey Tail). On red(?) maple. Hidden Forest.
Tricholoma aestans. With white pine. Quaise.
Tricholoma pullum. With white pine. Quaise.
Tricholoma vaccinum (Russet-Scaly Trich). Sheep pen. Lost Farm.

Infrequent=found only once on Nantucket